

وزارة الصحة و البيئـة

المركز الوطني للتدريب و التنمية البشرية

The National Center for Training and Development

يرحب بكم

Pediatric Psychiatry Training Course

February 7-11, 2021

Prof (Hon.) Aamir Jalal Al Mosawi

Advisor Doctor/Expert trainer

Accreditation

This course was accredited by the National Center of Training and Development because it was accredited in 2018 by Iraq headquarter of Copernicus scientists international panel.

Accreditation

This course was accredited to be given in English language, but you are free to make comments and discussions in Arabic or English as you wish.

You can also ask for more clarifications in Arabic, if anything said was not clear.

Why this course was accredited?

- This course was accredited because the main principles of the course and the core scientific content were published in a book with international publisher.

The course book

Child psychiatry is a branch of pediatrics concerned with the diagnosis, treatment, and prevention of mental disorders in children, adolescents, and their families. Children can not be considered small adults and this fact can not be ignored when it comes to pediatric psychiatry. A board certified pediatric psychiatrist is available in the most developed countries like the United States, while pediatric psychiatry has not emerged as a separate subspecialty in many regions of the world. Adult psychiatrists by definition of their certificate are not qualified to deal with childhood psychiatric disorders. Therefore, there has been a demand that pediatricians and family physicians have adequate clinical knowledge about childhood psychiatric disorders, so they can make the appropriate referral or providing satisfactory counseling and management when necessary. The aim of this book is to describe a training course entitled "Pediatric psychiatry: An accredited training course" which aims at providing introductory knowledge about the practice of pediatric psychiatry.

Child psychiatry

Aamir Al Mosawi

Pediatric psychiatry: An accredited training course

Aamir Jalal Al Mosawi, is advisor doctor in pediatrics and pediatric psychiatry at the Children Teaching Hospital of Baghdad Medical City. He is also advisor doctor and expert trainer at the National Training and Development Center of the Iraqi Ministry of Health. He is the Head of Iraq Headquarter of Copernicus Scientists International Panel.

978-613-9-86510-9

Al Mosawi

LAP LAMBERT
Academic Publishing

Main references

Aamir Al-Mosawi

The pattern of pervasive developmental disorders in Iraqi children

Pediatric Psychiatry

 LAMBERT
Academic Publishing

Categories > Social Sciences > Psychology > Psychiatry

100 Best Psychiatry Books of All Time

As featured on CNN, Forbes and Inc – BookAuthority identifies and rates the best books in the world, based on recommendations by thought leaders and experts.

We may earn a commission for purchases made through links in this page. [Learn more](#)

Recommendations by Vinod Khosla, Matt Haig, Neville Southall, Sarah Leah Whitson and 9 others

The Heartland

finding and losing schizophrenia

Nathan Filer (You?) | 2019 | ★★★★★ 4.77

In *The Heartland*, Nathan Filer, a former mental health nurse, invites us to spend time in the company of some extraordinary people whose lives have been affected by this most strange of human conditions, and to discover their complex, surprising, painful, funny and ultimately relatable stories. Interlacing these first person encounters with a series of meditative essays, he debunks myths, challenges orthodoxy and offers fresh insight into what is traditionally considered to be psychiatry's heartland: the diagnosis and treatment of schizophrenia. ...more

Recommended by Matt Haig, The Mental Elf and Suzi Gage

The pattern of pervasive developmental disorders in Iraqi children

Pediatric Psychiatry

Aamir Al-Mosawi (You?) | 2019 | ★★★★★ 4.25

Little is known about the pattern of pervasive developmental disorders in Iraq. This is a retrospective clinical study aiming at describing the pattern of pervasive developmental disorders in Iraqi children observed at the pediatric psychiatry clinic in a tertiary pediatric referral center. During nine months period (18 November 2018 to 18 July 2019), fifty one patients with pervasive developmental disorders (30 males and 21 females) were observed at the psychiatry clinic at the Children Teaching Hospital of Baghdad Medical City. In this series, typical autism without significant mental retardation accounted for 65%. ...more

Recommended by Scientists Panel

Scientists Panel Bookauthority's Best Psychiatry Books of All Time
<https://bookauthority.org/books/best-psychiatry-books>

Read Amazon reviews | Rate or write a review

[View on Amazon](#)

[Enjoy Unlimited Reading](#)

Main references

Gilles de la Tourette syndrome is a neuro-psychiatric disorder that generally affects children with normal intelligence and can affect also talented children. Gilles de la Tourette syndrome was first described in a book entitled "Malleus Maleficarum" which means "Witch's hammer" in the late 15th century. The book described a priest whose abnormal involuntary repetitive behaviors were considered to be related to possession by the devil. In the medical literature, Jean Marc Gaspard Itard, a French doctor was the first to describe a patient with this syndrome in 1825. The rather bizarre manifestations of the syndrome including involuntary movements and utterances can make an intelligent child a victim of the condition, and adversely affects his schooling and results in social rejection and consequently isolation. Awareness of this condition by the community, educators, and also medical practitioners are necessary to avoid the loss of affected children who can have the potential to be a talented individual in the future. Gilles de la Tourette syndrome has not been described or documented before in Iraq. The aim of this book is to describe the first case of this syndrome in Iraq.

Aamir Al Mosawi

Gilles de la Tourette syndrome

Pediatric psychiatry

Aamir Jalal Al Mosawi is advisor in pediatrics and pediatric psychiatry at the Children Teaching Hospital of Baghdad Medical City. He is the Head of Iraq Headquarter of Copernicus Scientists International Panel. He served as a member of the advisory council the International Association of Medical Colleges (IAMC).

978-613-9-84376-3

 LAMBERT
Academic Publishing

Main references

Down syndrome (Trisomy 21) was first described by Jean-Etienne-Dominique Esquirol in 1838 and later by Edouard Séguin in 1846. However, the disorder was named after John Langdon Down, a British physician who emphasized that the syndrome is a distinct form of mental retardation in 1862. Down syndrome is the most common chromosomal disorder in humans, and its recognition is one of the basic skills needed by medical practitioners, family doctors, pediatricians, and even medical students. This book and the Atlas which is providing represent a valuable tool for mastering the recognition of this condition.

Aamir Al Mosawi

Down syndrome Atlas

Aamir Jalal Al Mosawi is advisor in pediatrics and pediatric psychiatry at the Children Teaching Hospital of Baghdad Medical City. He is the Head of Iraq Headquarter of Copernicus Scientists International Panel. He served as a member of the advisory council the International Association of Medical Colleges (IAMC).

978-613-9-58120-7

LAP LAMBERT
Academic Publishing

Accreditation of training courses

What is accreditation of a training course?
Have you attended an accredited training course?

Accreditation of training courses

An accreditation of a training course occurs when an independent scientific body evaluates a training course, the training methodology used in the course, and the qualifications of the trainers and lecturers of the course and approve the course.

**Certificate
of attendance and
successful completion**

CERTIFICATE OF ACHIEVEMENT IS HEREBY AWARDED
TO

TO RECOGNIZE SUCCESSFUL PARTICIPATION IN
Pediatric psychiatry training course

February 7-11, 2021

مُنْتَادِر س. جَابِر
مَدِير المَرْكَزِ الوَطَنِيِّ
لِلتَدْرِيبِ وَالتَّوَسُّطِ
بِالْبَحْثِ البَشَرِيِّ

Dr. Muntadar S. Jaber
Director of The National Center of
Training and Development

عَامِر المَسَوِي
مُشَاوِر دَوَّابٍ وَخَبِير مُتَدَرِّب

Aamir Al Mosawi
Advisor Doctor and Expert Trainier

Accreditation of training courses

Accreditation of a training course is the single most important method which can guarantee the adherence of the course to the scientific standards and ensure avoiding wasting of time of the participants , and also wasting resources during training.

Course Category

- This is a specialized medical course which is considered a short intensive course that aims at introducing essential principles and providing foundation skills.

Main aims

- 1-Providing the participants an introductory knowledge about the practice of pediatric psychiatry and common childhood psychiatric disorders.**
- 2-Prividing the participants the foundation skills of the practice pediatric psychiatry.**

Main aims

Knowledge and skills acquired during the course are expected to help the participants in overcoming the diagnostic and therapeutic challenges and problems when facing a child with psychiatric condition, and also help in making the appropriate referral as necessary.

Learning objectives of the course

- **After the course, the participants are expected to have satisfactory knowledge, skills, and understanding, when it comes to the general practices of pediatric psychiatry and common childhood psychiatric disorders.**

Training methods

- Training sessions' worksheets will be used in association with the other training activities such as mini-lectures, presentations, activities, practical case studies.

Course final exam

- **Course final exam:** One of the important aims of the course final exam is to consolidate the knowledge learnt during the course.
- **Source:** All the questions are from the power point presentations and the worksheets given during the course.
- **Exam format:** multiple choice questions (MCQs).

Ice breaking activity

Ice breaking activity

- We will begin the course with an ice breaking activity
- Do you know what an ice breaking activity is?

Ice breaking activity

- It has become an orthodox to begin courses with an ice breaking activity where participants introduce themselves and give a brief account about their experiences relevant to the theme of course.
- Ice breaking activity help the participants to adapt to the course environment.

Ice breaking activity

We want each participant to introduce himself/herself by answering the following questions:

- **What is your name?**
- **What is your job title?**
- **Where are you working now?**
- **Have you worked in other places before?**
- **Do you have any experiences in the field of pediatric psychiatry?**

ACTIVITY

Take five minutes to write:

Three childhood psychiatric problems that you have observed.

The five most important or most common childhood psychiatric problems in your opinion.

Module 1: Pediatric psychiatry and childhood mental disorders

- **Children can not be considered a small adults and this fact can not be ignored when it comes to pediatric psychiatry.**

Pediatric psychiatry and childhood mental disorders

- **Childhood psychiatric disorders commonly present with abnormal developmental progress in one or more domains of development rather than specific symptoms observed in adults with psychiatric disorders.**

Pediatric psychiatry and childhood mental disorders

- **The discipline of pediatric psychiatry evolved with the increasing knowledge and understanding of the child development.**

Pediatric psychiatry and childhood mental disorders

- **Thomas Willis (27,January 1621-11, November 1675) was the first doctor to describe mental retardation as a disease of the brain.**

Pediatric psychiatry and childhood mental disorders

- **In 1867, Henry Maudsley, a British physician (1835-1918) emphasized the possibility of mental disorders in children when he included a chapter entitled “Insanity of Early Life” in his book “Physiology and Pathology of Mind”.**

Pediatric psychiatry and childhood mental disorders

Henry Maudsley attempted to correlate symptoms with the patient's developmental status at the time of onset of the mental disorders.

Pediatric psychiatry and childhood mental disorders

- **In 1887, the German physician Hermann Emminghaus published a landmark book in child psychiatry entitled “Psychic Disturbances in Childhood”**
been
called
“The cradle of child psychiatr

Pediatric psychiatry and childhood mental disorders

- **Significant advances in the developmental psychology during the early 1900s helped paving the way for pediatric psychiatry to become a discipline particularly in the developed countries.**

Pediatric psychiatry and childhood mental disorders

- **These early 1900s advances were preceded by the work of Wilhelm Preyer, a German physiologist who in 1882 published a book entitled “The Mind of the Child” . In this book Preyer presented his observations on the development of his son from birth to the age of three years.**

Pediatric psychiatry and childhood mental disorders

- The first academic child psychiatry department in the world was established in 1930 by one of the most influential American clinical pediatric psychiatrists of the 20th century, Leo Kanner

Child and childhood mental disorders

- **In 1943, Leo Kanner described the syndrome of infantile autism which was called by some authors “Kanner's Syndrome” (Neumärker, 2003). The succinct clinical descriptions made by Kanner of autism remains valid and useful until now.**

Pediatric psychiatry and childhood mental disorders

- **Kanner published a breakthrough article entitled "Autistic disturbances of affective contact". He described an eleven children (3 girls and 8 boys) having high intelligence, a strong desire for aloneness, and an obsessive insistence on persistent sameness. Kanner called the condition later "early infantile autism.**

Module 2: Nosology of pediatric psychiatric disorders

- **Childhood psychiatric disorders are generally divided into two broad categories including disorders that are mostly begin during childhood, and adult psychiatric disorders that are seen during childhood.**

Nosology of pediatric psychiatric disorders

Childhood psychiatric disorders that are mostly begin during childhood include:

A-Sleep disorders.

B-Childhood schizophrenia.

C-Eating disorders (Anorexia and bulimia)

D-Adjustment disorder.

E-All of the above.

F-Non of the above.

Nosology of pediatric psychiatric disorders

Adult psychiatric disorders seen during childhood include all of the following except:

A-Anxiety disorders.

B-Tic disorders including Tourette's syndrome

C-Mood disorders.

D-Sleep and eating disorders.

Nosology of pediatric psychiatric disorders

- **Childhood psychiatric disorders that are mostly begin during childhood:**

A-Developmental psychiatric disorders

D-Disruptive behavior disorders

C-Elimination disorders (Enuresis and encopresis)

D-Feeding disorders (Rumination and pica)

E-All of the above.

Nosology of pediatric psychiatric disorders

Childhood psychiatric disorders that are mostly begin during childhood:

A-Tic disorders including Tourette syndrome

B-

Childhood anxiety disorders (selective mutism, seperation anxiety disorder, and reactive attachment disorder).

C-Habit disorders.

D-All of the above.

Nosology of pediatric psychiatric disorders

Childhood developmental psychiatric disorders include:

A-Mental retardation.

B-Enuresis and encopresis.

C-Eating disorder.

D-All of the above.

E-None of the above.

Nosology of pediatric psychiatric disorders

All of the followings are developmental psychiatric disorders except:

A-Mental retardation

B-Kanner's syndrome

C-Asperger syndrome

D-Stuttering

E-Learning disability

F-Tic disorders

Nosology of pediatric psychiatric disorders

Pervasive developmental disorders include:

A-Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder.

B-Oppositional defiant disorder.

C-Conduct disorder.

D-All of the above.

E-None of the above.

Nosology of pediatric psychiatric disorders

Adult psychiatric disorders seen during childhood include all of the following except:

A-Anxiety disorders.

B-Tic disorders including Tourette's syndrome

C-Mood disorders.

D-Sleep and eating disorders.

Nosology of pediatric psychiatric disorders

Mood disorders include:

A-Panic disorders.

B-Specific & Social Phobias

C-Post-traumatic stress disorders

D-Obsessive compulsive disorders

E-All of the above.

F-Non of the above.

Module 3: The DSM

Pediatricians and family physicians who would like to study childhood psychiatric disorders will very likely come across the term DSM.

Who knows what is the DSM?

The DSM

The DSM is

A-Nomenclature and definitions book.

B-A psychiatry conference.

C-Bible of psychiatry in the United States of America.

D-A and C.

E-All of the above.

F-Non of the above.

The American psychiatric association's Diagnostic Statistical Manual of mental disorders (DSM)

Although this book, the DSM is not used in all countries of the world, it has been used by many psychiatrists inside and outside the United States. In the United States of America, many would like to call it the bible of psychiatry.

The American psychiatric association's Diagnostic Statistical Manual of mental disorders (DSM)

The American psychiatric association's Diagnostic Statistical Manual of mental disorders (DSM)

It is very desirable for pediatric psychiatrists and other physicians such as pediatricians and family physicians who would like to study childhood psychiatric disorders to have an

The American psychiatric association's Diagnostic Statistical Manual of mental disorders (DSM)

Which of the following statements is true:

A-The DSM is a publication of the American Psychiatry Association.

B-The DSM is not used in all countries of the world.

C-The DSM generated controversy and debate.

D-The DSM was criticized for the subtypes of autism disorder

E-All of the above.

Conclusion remarks

- Today, in the introductory talks we emphasized the importance of accreditation of training courses, and we had an introductory module about the historic evolution of pediatric psychiatry.
- We also talked about the nosology of pediatric psychiatric disorders and the importance of knowing what is the DSM.

Thank you for joining us today. I hope you are all satisfied for what you came for.

وزارة الصحة و البيئة

المركز الوطني للتدريب و التنمية البشرية

The National Center for Training and Development

مرحبكم

REFERENNCES

- Al-Mosawi AJ. Pediatric psychiatry: An accredited training course. 1st ed., Saarbrücken; LAP Lambert Academic Publishing: 2018 (ISBN: 978-613-9-86510-9).
- Al-Mosawi AJ. The use of cerebrolysin and citicoline in autism and Asperger syndrome. *Journal of Bio Innovation* 2019 January; 8(1): 99-108.
- Al-Mosawi AJ. New therapies for Rett syndrome. *Journal of Bio Innovation* 2019 May; 8(3): 301-307.
- Al-Mosawi AJ. Heller syndrome in two Iraqi children. *Clinical Research and Trials* 2019 August 26; Volume 5: 1-3. 10.15761/CRT.1000271
- Al-Mosawi AJ. Pervasive developmental disorders in Iraqi children. *Journal of Psychiatry Research Reviews & Reports* 2019 Sep 11; 1(1): 1-8. Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.4007395
- Al-Mosawi AJ. The etiology of mental retardation in Iraqi children. *SunKrist Journal of Neonatology and Pediatrics*.2019 June 21; 1(1):1-9. Article No: sjnp-v1-1001. Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.3878451
- Al-Mosawi AJ. Our experience with childhood pervasive developmental disorders (Autism and Asperger Syndrome): Cure is Possible. *EC Clinical and Medical Case Reports* 2020; 3(4): 01-08. Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.3892198
- Al-Mosawi AJ. A Unique experience with mental and developmental retardation: Innovative Medical therapies for idiopathic mental retardation. *EC Clinical and Medical Case Reports* 2020; 3(5): 42-54. Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.3892214
- Al-Mosawi AJ. Treatment of A Boy with Idiopathic Mental Retardation: From Uneducable to Educable. *Progressing Aspects in Pediatrics and Neonatology* 2020 August 10; 2 (5): 197-202. Doi: 10. 32474/ PAPN. 2020. 02.000149
- Al-Mosawi AJ. Case Studies in Pediatric Psychiatry: An Approach to Deep Learning and Experience Acquisition. *SunKrist Journal of Psychiatry and Mental Health* 2020 August 21; 1(1): 1-21[1004] .Doi: <https://doi.org/10.46940/sjpmh.01.1004>
- Al-Mosawi AJ. Childhood trichotillomania: A case and a review of the available evidence-based pharmacologic therapies. *Sunkrist Journal of Psychiatry and Mental Health* 2020 Dec 10; 1 (2):1-7. Doi: 10. 5281/ zenodo.4376109
- Al-Mosawi AJ. Atypical autism associated with elevated gonadotrophin and precocious puberty: A Very rare association or a new clinical syndrome? *Biomedical Journal of Scientific & Technical Research* 2021 Jan, 21; 33(2): 25686-25689. Doi10.26717/BJSTR.2021.33.005377
- Al-Mosawi AJ. Asperger syndrome and regressive autism.1st ed., Saarbrücken; LAP Lambert Academic Publishing: 2018(ISBN: 978-613-9-82643-8).
- Al-Mosawi AJ. A new therapeutic approach for pervasive developmental disorders. 1st ed., Saarbrücken; LAP Lambert Academic Publishing: 2018 (ISBN: 978-3-659-86602-9).
- Al-Mosawi AJ. A novel therapeutic approach for idiopathic mental retardation. 1st ed., Saarbrücken; LAP Lambert Academic Publishing: 2018 (ISBN: 978-613-9-81808-2).
- Al-Mosawi AJ. The pattern of mental retardation in Iraqi children.1st ed., Saarbrücken; LAP Lambert Academic Publishing: 2019 (ISBN: 978-613-9-47350-2).

Al-Mosawi AJ. The pattern of pervasive developmental disorders in Iraqi children. 1st ed., Saarbrücken; LAP Lambert Academic Publishing: 2019 (ISBN: 978-3-330-05029-7).

Al-Mosawi AJ. Case studies in pediatric psychiatry: An approach to deep learning. 1st ed., Saarbrücken; LAP Lambert Academic Publishing: 2020 (ISBN: 978-620-2-52071-3).

Al-Mosawi AJ. Autism disorders: Cure is possible. 1st ed., Saarbrücken; LAP Lambert Academic Publishing, Saarbrücken; Germany, 2020 (ISBN-13:978-620-2-66617-6, ISBN-10: 620266617X).

Al-Mosawi AJ. Cure of autistic disorders: Our unique experience .1st ed., Saarbrücken; LAP Lambert Academic Publishing: 2020 (ISBN: 978-620-2-67716-5).

Al-Mosawi AJ. Gilles De La Tourette syndrome: A case and a brief review of the early documentation of the syndrome in the literature. International Journal of Psychiatry (ISSN: 2475-5435) 2020 Nov 26; 5(3): 1-4.

وزارة الصحة و البيئة
المركز الوطني للتدريب و التنمية البشرية
The National Center for Training and Human Development
تأسس عام ١٩٨٥

Certificate
of attendance and
successful completion

وزارة الصحة العراقية
Iraqi Ministry of Health
Founded 1920

CERTIFICATE OF ACHIEVEMENT IS HEREBY AWARDED

TO **Dr. Rahma Muthana Abdul-jabbar**

TO RECOGNIZE SUCCESSFUL PARTICIPATION IN
Pediatric psychiatry training course

February 7-11, 2021

مستشار
التدريب والتنمية
د. منتادار س. جابر

Dr. Muntadar S. Jaber
Director of The National Center of
Training and Development

مستشار
التدريب والتنمية
د. أمير آل موسى

Aamir Al Mosawi
Advisor Doctor and Expert Trainer

Certificate
of attendance and
successful completion

وزارة الصحة العراقية
Iraqi Ministry of Health
Founded 1920

CERTIFICATE OF ACHIEVEMENT IS HEREBY AWARDED

TO **Dr.Sarah Jawad Kadhim**

TO RECOGNIZE SUCCESSFUL PARTICIPATION IN
Pediatric psychiatry training course

February 7-11, 2021

مستشار
التدريب والتطوير
الدكتور مونتادار جابر

Dr.Muntadar S.Jaber
Director of The National Center of
Training and Development

مستشار
التدريب والتطوير
الدكتور امير موسى

Aamir Al Mosawi
Advisor Doctor and Expert Trainer

Certificate
of attendance and
successful completion

وزارة الصحة العراقية
Iraqi Ministry of Health
Founded 1920

CERTIFICATE OF ACHIEVEMENT IS HEREBY AWARDED

TO **Dr. Zaianab Jawad Kadhim**

TO RECOGNIZE SUCCESSFUL PARTICIPATION IN
Pediatric psychiatry training course

February 7-11, 2021

مستشار
التدريب والتنمية
د. منطادار س. جابر

Dr. Muntadar S. Jaber
Director of The National Center of
Training and Development

مستشار
التدريب والتنمية
د. أمير آل ماضي

Aamir Al Mosawi
Advisor Doctor and Expert Trainer

Certificate
of attendance and
successful completion

وزارة الصحة العراقية
Iraqi Ministry of Health
Founded 1920

CERTIFICATE OF ACHIEVEMENT IS HEREBY AWARDED

TO **Dr. Duha Fakhri Jassim**

TO RECOGNIZE SUCCESSFUL PARTICIPATION IN
Pediatric psychiatry training course

February 7-11, 2021

د. منتادار س. جابر
مديرة المركز الوطني للتدريب والتطوير

Dr. Muntadar S. Jaber
Director of The National Center of
Training and Development

د. أمير آل ماضي
مستشار طبيب وأخصائي تدريب

Aamir Al Mosawi
Advisor Doctor and Expert Trainer

Certificate
of attendance and
successful completion

وزارة الصحة العراقية
Iraqi Ministry of Health
Founded 1920

CERTIFICATE OF ACHIEVEMENT IS HEREBY AWARDED

TO **Dr. Sinan Essam Al-Jarah**

TO RECOGNIZE SUCCESSFUL PARTICIPATION IN
Pediatric psychiatry training course

February 7-11, 2021

د. منتادار س. جابر
مدير المركز الوطني للتدريب والتطوير

Dr. Muntadar S. Jaber
Director of The National Center of
Training and Development

د. أمير الموسوي
مستشار طبيب وأخصائي مدرب

Aamir Al Mosawi
Advisor Doctor and Expert Trainer

Certificate
of attendance and
successful completion

وزارة الصحة العراقية
Iraqi Ministry of Health
Founded 1920

CERTIFICATE OF ACHIEVEMENT IS HEREBY AWARDED

TO **Dr. Bashar Mohammed Hooobi**

TO RECOGNIZE SUCCESSFUL PARTICIPATION IN
Pediatric psychiatry training course

February 7-11, 2021

د. منتادار س. جابر
مدير المركز الوطني للتدريب والتطوير

Dr. Muntadar S. Jaber

**Director of The National Center of
Training and Development**

د. أمير آل مرساوي
مستشار طبيب وأخصائي تدريب

Aamir Al Mosawi
Advisor Doctor and Expert Trainer

Certificate
of attendance and
successful completion

وزارة الصحة العراقية
Iraqi Ministry of Health
Founded 1920

CERTIFICATE OF ACHIEVEMENT IS HEREBY AWARDED

TO **Dr. Raghdaa Dheyaa Sadeq**

TO RECOGNIZE SUCCESSFUL PARTICIPATION IN
Pediatric psychiatry training course

February 7-11, 2021

مستشار
التدريب والتطوير
الدكتور
مونتادار س. جابر

Dr. Muntadar S. Jaber
Director of The National Center of
Training and Development

مستشار
التدريب والتطوير
الدكتور
عامر آل موسى

Aamir Al Mosawi
Advisor Doctor and Expert Trainer

Certificate
of attendance and
successful completion

وزارة الصحة العراقية
Iraqi Ministry of Health
Founded 1920

CERTIFICATE OF ACHIEVEMENT IS HEREBY AWARDED

TO **Dr. Hind Amer Rasheed**

TO RECOGNIZE SUCCESSFUL PARTICIPATION IN
Pediatric psychiatry training course

February 7-11, 2021

مستشار
التدريب والتطوير
الدكتور
مونتادار س. جابر

Dr. Muntadar S. Jaber
Director of The National Center of
Training and Development

مستشار
التدريب والتطوير
الدكتور
عامر الموسوي

Aamir Al Mosawi
Advisor Doctor and Expert Trainer

Certificate
of attendance and
successful completion

وزارة الصحة العراقية
Iraqi Ministry of Health
Founded 1920

CERTIFICATE OF ACHIEVEMENT IS HEREBY AWARDED

TO **Dr. Kadhim Kudair Abbas**

TO RECOGNIZE SUCCESSFUL PARTICIPATION IN
Pediatric psychiatry training course

February 7-11, 2021

مستشار
التدريب والتطوير
الدكتور مونتادار جابر

Dr. Muntadar S. Jaber
Director of The National Center of
Training and Development

مستشار
التدريب والتطوير
الدكتور امير موسى

Aamir Al Mosawi
Advisor Doctor and Expert Trainer

Certificate
of attendance and
successful completion

وزارة الصحة العراقية
Iraqi Ministry of Health
Founded 1920

CERTIFICATE OF ACHIEVEMENT IS HEREBY AWARDED

TO **Dr. Amenah Mohsin Jasim**

TO RECOGNIZE SUCCESSFUL PARTICIPATION IN
Pediatric psychiatry training course

February 7-11, 2021

مستشار
التدريب والتنمية
الوطنية

Dr. Muntadar S. Jaber
Director of The National Center of
Training and Development

مستشار
التدريب والتنمية
الوطنية

Aamir Al Mosawi
Advisor Doctor and Expert Trainer

DSC_22121MOV

DSC_2212.MOV

DSC_2212.MOV

DSC_2212.MOV

DSC_2212.MOV

DSC_2212.MOV

DSC_2212.MOV

DSC_2214.MOV

مركز التطوير والتدريب (مركز) ووزارة الصحة و البيئة

The National Center for Training and Development

مركز التطوير والتدريب

وزارة الصحة و البيئة

المركز الوطني للتدريب والتنمية البشرية

The National Center for Training and Development

مرحباً بكم

وزارة الصحة و البنية التحتية

المركز الوطني للتدريب والتنمية البشرية

The National Center for Training and Development

مرحبكم

